

Study protocol

Promoting critical health literacy through microlearning in secondary schools: A feasibility study using the example of interpreting risk reductions in mathematics education

Version: 01

Date: 15 May 2025

Research Team

Principal investigator

Name	Prof. Dr. phil. Anke Steckelberg
Institution	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Medical Faculty, University Medicine Halle, Institute of Health, Midwifery and Nursing Science
Address	Magdeburger Str. 8, 06112 Halle (Saale)
Phone	0345 557-1220
E-Mail	anke.steckelberg@medizin.uni-halle.de

Collaborating researchers

Name	Sandro Zacher
Institution	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Medical Faculty, University Medicine Halle, Institute of Health, Midwifery and Nursing Science
E-Mail	sandro.zacher@medizin.uni-halle.de

Name	Dr. Jana Hinneburg
Institution	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Medical Faculty, University Medicine Halle, Institute of Health, Midwifery and Nursing Science
E-Mail	jana.hinneburg@medizin.uni-halle.de

Name	Jana Kaden
Institution	University of Bremen, Institute for Public Health and Nursing Research, Bremen, Germany
E-Mail	jana.kaden@uni-bremen.de

Name	Prof. Julia Lühnen
Institution	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Institute of Clinical Nursing Science, Berlin, Germany
E-Mail	julia.luehnen@charite.de

1. Abstract

Background

The increasing availability of health information online presents a challenge for young people, who must learn to distinguish trustworthy from misleading content. Critical health literacy is essential for enabling individuals to question health information and make informed decisions. Relative risk measures often appear more persuasive than absolute ones, potentially leading to an overestimation of the benefits of medical interventions. Mathematics curricula already address relative and absolute frequencies. Integrating health-related examples into mathematics lessons may provide an opportunity to foster critical health literacy. Microlearning modules offer a promising approach by delivering focused, concise content.

Objectives

This study will investigate the feasibility of integrating an existing microlearning module on interpreting risk reductions in health contexts into the mathematics curriculum of secondary schools. It will explore the needs and requirements of pupils and teachers and will further develop the module through a co-design process with pupils.

Methods

Aligned with the MRC framework for complex interventions, this study will focus on the intervention development and adaptation phase. Conducted in the context of secondary school mathematics education, the study will comprise several phases. Phase 1 will involve a focus group interview with mathematics teachers to assess content, pedagogical, technical, and organisational needs. Phases 2 and 3 will be integrated into regular school activities and will involve both an assessment of pupils' knowledge on interpreting risk reductions (using a validated instrument) and a co-design process to adapt the microlearning module. The co-design process will include four workshops in which pupils will test the module, provide feedback, and contribute to its redesign. Data collection will include participant observation, feedback cards, and documentation of group work. Qualitative data will be analysed using content analysis; knowledge test results will be analysed using Rasch modelling.

Expected Outcomes

The needs assessment with teachers and the co-design process with pupils are expected to provide insights into which content, formats, and interaction methods will be most effective in communicating

the concepts of relative and absolute risk reduction to year 9 pupils. It is also anticipated that adaptations to the microlearning module will be required to optimise its usability and integration into mathematics teaching.

2. Background

The availability of health information is steadily increasing. Young people, in particular, are increasingly using online sources to find information on topics such as chronic diseases, mental health, fitness and nutrition [1]. This development offers potential to strengthen their decision-making skills. At the same time, the flood of contradictory and misleading information poses a challenge, as it is becoming increasingly difficult to assess the trustworthiness of health information correctly [2-4]. In order to filter reliable sources from this multitude of information and to make informed decisions based on them, a critical analysis of content is required [4].

Critically appraising health information is part of critical health literacy [5]. This includes the ability to critically evaluate information about treatment effects and medical interventions [6]. International and national initiatives have long advocated for promoting health literacy from an early age, during childhood and adolescence [7, 8]. One way to implement this is through education in schools.

The Informed Health Choices working group has defined key concepts required for critically engaging with health claims. Interpreting statistical data is particularly challenging. One key concept focuses on the interpretation of treatment effects presented as relative effects [4]. Studies show that many people experience difficulties in interpreting these correctly. Presenting relative risk measures often appears more impressive than absolute risk measures and may lead to an overestimation of the benefit of a treatment or intervention [9-13].

This can be illustrated using the example of risk reduction: Relative risk reduction describes the percentage difference in event rates between the control and intervention groups, relative to the baseline risk in the control group. For example, if the risk of an event is 10% in the control group and 5% in the intervention group, the relative risk reduction is 50%. However, the same 50% relative risk reduction applies if the risk in the control group is only 2% and 1% in the intervention group. The actual benefit for the individual remains unclear, as the absolute number of people affected is not taken into account.

Absolute risk reduction, by contrast, indicates the actual difference in risk between the two groups. If the risk is 10% in the control group and 5% in the intervention group, the absolute risk reduction is 5%, meaning that five out of 100 people treated will benefit from the intervention.

Comprehensive teaching programmes based on the Informed Health Choices key concepts have been developed and evaluated for primary and secondary schools [14-17]. Another way to promote critical health literacy is to integrate these concepts into existing curricula using microlearning modules. Microlearning is characterised by concise and focused delivery of information covering a self-contained subtopic within a broader theme [18]. An example of such a microlearning module is the RiskTool, a web-based, self-directed learning unit that supports users in interpreting and calculating risk reductions. It conveys content through case studies, visualisations, and interactive exercises and was originally developed for both lay audiences and healthcare professionals [19]. Mathematics lessons provide a suitable context for integrating health-related examples. The interpretation of data using statistical parameters and the solving of intra- and extra-mathematical application tasks are integral parts of the curriculum. In addition, pupils are expected to justify mathematical statements both in everyday language and using technical terminology and to critically examine mathematical content [20]. Integrating the RiskTool into mathematics lessons could therefore offer an opportunity to promote critical health literacy among pupils.

This study will examine whether a microlearning module can be integrated into mathematics lessons as a health-related example and what content-related, didactic, organisational, and technical requirements are associated with such integration.

3. Aims

The overarching aim of this study is to test the integration of a microlearning module on interpreting health-related statements as an application example within the curriculum of general education schools. This will be explored using the example of the Informed Health Choices key concept 'Be cautious of relative effects alone' [21] within year 9 mathematics lessons. An existing web-based microlearning module (RiskTool) on relative and absolute risk reduction will be used and further developed for this purpose.

Specific objectives are as follows:

- Participatory adaptation and further development of the microlearning module with pupils through a co-design process
- Identification of the needs and requirements of pupils and teachers for integrating the module into mathematics lessons
- Exploration of pupils' knowledge regarding the interpretation of risk reductions

4. Methods

4.1 Design

The study will follow a participatory research approach and will employ a co-design process using both qualitative and quantitative methods. Co-design refers to the active collaboration between researchers, users, and stakeholders in developing solutions [22]. In this study, solutions will be developed to support the integration of teaching about relative and absolute risk interpretation into mathematics lessons. In this context, the users and stakeholders will be pupils and teachers.

Due to the various components of the microlearning module and the numerous contextual factors that may influence the intervention, the MRC framework for complex interventions [23] will serve as the conceptual framework. The study will be classified within the phase of intervention development and adaptation.

The iterative co-design process will enable the continuous adaptation of the microlearning module, taking into account pupils' specific needs and the requirements of mathematics teaching. In addition, school framework conditions, curricular integration, and teachers' needs will be systematically incorporated into the adaptation process to ensure practical and acceptable implementation.

4.2 Description of the Intervention

The microlearning module to be used in this study, known as the RiskTool [24], has already been developed and piloted [19]. The RiskTool was designed as a self-directed and interactive micro e-learning programme, informed by theories of adult education [25], instructional design [26, 27], and multimedia design [28]. It teaches critical interpretation and calculation of relative and absolute risk reductions necessary to evaluate claims about health topics and interventions.

Following completion of the RiskTool, users will be able to:

- Interpret risk reductions and describe the meaning of a correct interpretation
- Calculate absolute and relative risk reduction
- Interpret the influence of baseline risk on absolute risk reduction
- Analyse relative risk reduction in a real-life example and derive absolute risk reduction

To achieve these learning objectives, the RiskTool is structured into four sections:

Section 1: Highlights the relevance of the topic and provides users with an opportunity to identify potential knowledge gaps, thereby increasing motivation

Section 2: Introduces the basic principles of risk reduction through a case study illustrating the difference between absolute and relative risk reduction, including step-by-step mathematical derivation and a consolidation exercise

Section 3: Explores the influence of baseline risk. Using a case study, users will calculate absolute and relative risk reductions for individuals with different baseline risks to analyse how absolute risk reduction changes while relative risk reduction remains constant

Section 4: Offers a series of interactive exercises for practical application and consolidation. Users will be guided step-by-step through calculating event rates and using 2x2 tables, with the RiskTool providing real-time feedback and corrections

The initial feasibility piloting and iterative revision were conducted with individuals without prior medical knowledge and with professionals from various health sectors using qualitative methods. The RiskTool has been shown to be applicable and relevant for these target groups [19].

4.3 Study Procedure

Figure 1: Study Procedure

The study will be divided into four central phases. In the first phase, a needs assessment will be conducted with mathematics teachers to explore the applicability of the RiskTool and to identify technical and organisational requirements for its integration into mathematics lessons.

In the second phase, pupils' knowledge regarding the interpretation and calculation of risk reductions in health contexts will be assessed. This assessment will provide the basis for the subsequent co-design process.

The third phase will consist of a co-design process implemented through four workshops. In the first workshop (approximately 135 minutes), pupils will be given access to the RiskTool. After using the module, a group exercise will be conducted to assess feasibility and to identify pupils' needs, from which adaptation requirements will be derived. In the second and third workshop (approximately 270 minutes), pupils will work in groups to design prototypes addressing these identified needs, such as case studies or exercises. In the fourth workshop (approximately 90

minutes), the developed prototypes will be presented, and components to be incorporated into the revised RiskTool will be selected.

In the fourth phase, the selected prototypes will be implemented into a revised version of the RiskTool.

4.4 Setting

The study will be conducted in a general education context at a secondary school in Saxony-Anhalt. Based on the mathematics curriculum for secondary schools in Saxony-Anhalt, year 9 has been selected as the target group [20].

In year 9, the competence area 'frequency distribution' includes the interpretation of data using parameters such as absolute and relative frequencies and the solving of intra- and extra-mathematical application tasks. In addition, pupils are expected to justify mathematical statements using both everyday language and mathematical terminology and to critically examine mathematical content.

The project will therefore be implemented as a school-based project in which no new content will be introduced, but existing curriculum content will be taught in an innovative way and transferred to new areas of application. To adapt the co-design process to the organisational circumstances of the school and the curricular requirements of mathematics teaching, a mathematics teacher will be involved in both the implementation of the study and in the project team.

4.5 Sample

For the needs assessment (Phase 1), mathematics teachers and trainee teachers at secondary schools will be selected using purposive sampling based on gender, professional experience, and curriculum responsibility. No additional inclusion or exclusion criteria will be applied. A sample of 6-8 teachers will be targeted to ensure that different perspectives are represented.

For the knowledge test and co-design process (Phases 2 and 3), 20-25 year 9 pupils will be included using a convenience sample. Pupils will be selected by the participating teacher and will consist of a voluntary learning group within the context of a school project. No specific inclusion or exclusion criteria will be applied.

4.6 Recruitment

To raise awareness of the study, the State Institute for School Quality and Teacher Training of Saxony-Anhalt was contacted by email with a summary of the study and was asked to forward a study flyer to the headteachers of secondary schools in the state. In addition, the study summary and flyer were sent to a headteacher of a secondary school that had previously participated in an earlier project.

A combined recruitment strategy will be used for the teacher needs assessment. Firstly, headteachers will act as gatekeepers for recruiting teachers within their own schools and in collaborating schools. This will take place via personal contact or email. Secondly, recruitment will also be conducted via the working group responsible for the development of the mathematics curriculum [20]. For recruitment of pupils, information about the study will be passed on to mathematics teachers via the headteacher, with the aim of recruiting one teacher to participate in the study. Together with this teacher, a suitable

format for integrating the study into the school curriculum will be determined (e.g. as a project week or as part of an extracurricular programme), and an appropriate learning group will be selected.

4.7 Information and consent process

For the first study phase (teacher needs assessment), information about the study will be provided via an information sheet following initial contact with interested teachers by email or in person. Teachers will have the opportunity to contact the study team by telephone or email with any questions. Written informed consent will be obtained prior to data collection, and verbal consent will be confirmed again shortly before the group interview.

For the second and third study phases, minors will be included. Two weeks before the start of the study, pupils will receive an information sheet in age-appropriate language explaining the purpose, content, and scope of the study. This will be distributed by the participating teacher. Pupils will also have the opportunity to discuss any questions about the study with the teacher.

The information sheet and teacher explanation will make it clear that participation in the study is voluntary. In addition, pupils' legal guardians will receive an information sheet (distributed via the school's usual communication channels), containing the same information and providing the option to refuse participation.

Forms indicating refusal of participation will be collected by the teacher and kept anonymously until the end of the study, after which they will be destroyed. Pupils may withdraw from participation at any time without negative consequences. Pupils who choose not to participate will be able to attend the school's regular lessons.

The information and consent process was discussed in advance with the relevant school authority in Saxony-Anhalt and will be submitted to the ethics committee for final review.

4.8 Outcomes

The primary outcome of the study will be the feasibility of the RiskTool from the perspectives of both teachers and pupils. Following standard feasibility assessment frameworks [29], feasibility in this study will be measured in terms of acceptability, applicability, and comprehension. The operationalisation of these components and subcategories will draw on the existing categories developed during the RiskTool's earlier development and piloting, with the option to expand categories inductively [19]. In addition, pupils' competence in critically appraising risk reductions will be assessed. This will be measured using a validated instrument [30].

A further outcome will be the revision of the RiskTool's instructional design. The module's development was guided by the ADDIE model and motivating learning design principles [26, 27]. The

'analysis' phase will be informed by the teacher needs assessment, the knowledge test, and the first step of the co-design process with pupils. Design and development will take place iteratively throughout the co-design process, with existing content (learning objectives, resources, monitoring strategies, motivation strategies, and materials) revised and adapted to the target group.

Table 1: Own representation of the development steps of the instructional design [26] and motivating learning design [27]

Concept	Development steps
Analyse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying the performance gap • Defining the instructional objectives • Describing the target group • Analysing existing materials • Defining the form of instruction
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing of learning objectives/motivation objectives • Developing of motivational strategies • Developing of strategies for checking learning objectives
Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing the content • Developing the materials
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing the teachers
Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing and conducting the evaluation

4.9 Data collection

Data collection for the needs assessment with teachers will be conducted via group interviews, either online or in person. If conducted online, the Webex platform (Cisco) will be used. A semi-structured interview guide, adapted from previous projects, will be employed [19]. Approximately two weeks prior to the interview, participants will be given access to the RiskTool and will be asked to complete it before the interview. At the same time, they will complete an online questionnaire (via LimeSurvey) capturing demographic data (age, gender, professional experience, and curriculum responsibility). It is anticipated that completing the RiskTool will take approximately 30 minutes, and the group interview will last approximately 45 minutes.

Data collection with pupils will be fully integrated into regular school activities and will employ both qualitative and quantitative methods (Figure 2). Participation will be completely voluntary and anonymous. Pupils may decline participation at any time.

Figure 2: Data collection procedure for pupils

Pupils' competence in critically appraising risk reductions will be assessed at the beginning of the project, aligned with the curriculum topic of absolute and relative frequencies [20]. The survey will be conducted online via LimeSurvey using school hardware. The validated instrument [30] will consist of 15 items and will take approximately 20 minutes to complete. Age and gender will be recorded prior to the knowledge test.

The co-design process will take the form of group work with limited frontal teaching. Specific tasks will be assigned to the pupils for group work, which they will complete independently. These tasks may include compiling relevant examples to illustrate risk reduction, developing exercises, or identifying functional requirements for the RiskTool's use in lessons.

Participant observation will be conducted by multiple researchers, and group work will be moderated. A semi-structured observation protocol will be used to document the group work process and outcomes. In addition, feedback cards containing open-ended questions and graded response options will be used to document pupils' positive and negative impressions of each workshop. The feedback cards will be collected anonymously in an envelope. Visual tools such as mind maps will also be used to document group work outcomes.

4.10 Data analysis

The group interview for the teacher needs assessment will be audio-recorded and transcribed. Data will be analysed using qualitative content analysis according to Mayring, applying structuring and summarising methods [31]. A deductive category system based on the existing framework from the RiskTool's development and piloting will be used, with the option to expand categories inductively [19]. The data analysis is carried out by two people independently of each other. The deductive category system is used to structure the content of the material. Further topics are identified inductively. Finally, the content is summarised. The pupils' knowledge test will be analysed descriptively using Rasch's probabilistic test theory [32].

Data from participant observation, workshop outputs, and feedback cards will also be analysed using qualitative content analysis according to Mayring [31], using the same deductive and inductive approach. For the first workshop, material from the three data sources will be collated and structured independently by two researchers. Based on this, the category system will be revised. For the second,

third and fourth workshops, the revised system will be applied by one researcher and reviewed by a second. Content will then be summarised by one researcher and cross-checked by a second. Basic demographic characteristics of teachers and pupils will be analysed descriptively. The quantitative data from the feedback cards will be analysed descriptively.

4.11 Schedule and duration of study

The total duration of the study, including data collection, analysis, and finalisation of the revised RiskTool, will be approximately nine months. Implementation will be adapted to the individual needs of the school and learning group. The planned time commitment for study participants is as follows:

Pupils:

- Four workshops totalling 11 school lessons (45 minutes each)
- Knowledge test: approx. 20 minutes

Teachers:

- Preparation using the RiskTool: approx. 30 minutes
- Group interview: approx. 45 minutes

The precise schedule will be determined in consultation with the school leadership and participating teacher to ensure optimal integration of the study into everyday school activities.

5. Risk-benefit assessment

Investigating the integration of the RiskTool into mathematics lessons requires direct interaction with the target groups (pupils and teachers). A purely theoretical approach would not suffice, as key insights regarding acceptability, applicability, understanding, needs, and requirements can only be gained through practical application.

Participation in the study will offer pupils the opportunity to deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts by applying them to the interpretation of health-related statements. Teaching pupils to interpret relative and absolute risks may contribute to promoting critical health literacy. Participation will be fully integrated into regular lessons and will not constitute an additional time or content-related burden. Depending on the specific circumstances of each school, participation may take place during project days or as part of extracurricular programmes.

Data collection will be fully anonymised. Both pupils and their legal guardians will receive comprehensive information about the study. No names or contact details of pupils will be collected by the research team. In cases where legal guardians refuse consent, only the relevant teacher will be informed for

identification purposes. Nevertheless, there remains a minor risk of re-identification through the combination of indirect identifiers (e.g. age and gender), particularly in small samples. This risk is considered low and of minimal impact, as no sensitive data will be linked to these variables. Age and gender will only be collected within the knowledge test and will not be linked to other results. No subgroup analyses will be conducted based on age or gender. Furthermore, no school-specific identifiers will be stored in the dataset, and results will be analysed only in aggregate form.

Data collected through participant observation, feedback cards, and group work outputs will be stored without any personal identifiers. Where necessary, any identifiers (e.g. names written on group work results) will be removed prior to storage.

For teachers, participation in the study will provide the opportunity to test and potentially adopt innovative teaching materials applying mathematical concepts to real-life contexts. Developed materials will be made available to interested teachers upon study completion. All participants will thus contribute to advancing approaches to promote critical health literacy in general education settings.

Teacher data collected during the group interview will include age, gender, professional experience, and curriculum responsibility. Given the small sample size, there is some risk of re-identification. However, the associated risk is considered low, as no sensitive data will be linked to these variables. Teachers will be recruited from various schools to further reduce this risk. Any names mentioned during the interview will be anonymised in the transcript, and data will only be reported in aggregate form.

Participation will take place within the school setting and therefore poses minimal risk to participants. The knowledge test and co-design process may present some cognitive challenge to pupils, but this will be in line with normal school activities. Any potential frustration or uncertainty will be mitigated through support provided by the participating teacher. Participation will be voluntary, and non-participation will not negatively affect pupils' academic performance. Participants may withdraw at any time. As the study does not involve medical or diagnostic procedures, the occurrence of incidental findings is excluded.

6. Data management and data protection

No sensitive personal data as defined under Article 9 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will be collected. The data collected will include demographic information (age and gender of pupils and teachers), teachers' professional experience and curriculum responsibilities, statements regarding the feasibility of the RiskTool and requirements for its use (from the teacher focus group), and pupil responses from the knowledge test and co-design workshops.

Knowledge test data will be collected and stored in fully anonymised form. It will not be possible to link the data to individual participants retrospectively. The knowledge test will be conducted using LimeSurvey hosted by Martin Luther University's IT centre, in compliance with GDPR.

Data from the co-design process will be collected without personal identifiers. For teacher data collected during the focus group (age, gender, professional experience), informed consent will be obtained. All data will be analysed in anonymised form.

Data processing responsibility will lie with Sandro Zacher and Prof. Anke Steckelberg, in accordance with data protection regulations. Data will be stored on password-protected computers and secure servers at Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, as well as within the university's own Cloud-based cloud service. Only members of the research team will have access to the data. No data will be shared with third parties, and results will only be reported in aggregated, anonymised form.

Audio recordings of the teacher focus groups will be deleted after transcription. No audio, image, or video recordings of pupils will be made. Observation notes, workshop outputs, and feedback cards will be digitised, and original physical materials will be securely disposed of.

Data will be stored in accordance with data protection regulations for a period of ten years and will then be deleted.

7. Dealing with changes to the study protocol

Any significant changes to the study protocol will be made in consultation with the Ethics Committee of the Medical Faculty of Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg and will be documented in an updated version of the protocol. Any deviations will also be described in the study results report.

8. Expected outcomes

Based on the study objectives, several key outcomes are anticipated. The co-design process with pupils is expected to yield insights into which content, presentation formats, and interaction approaches are particularly suitable for communicating the concepts of relative and absolute risk reduction in an understandable and engaging manner for year 9 pupils.

The study will also provide insights into the extent to which the existing RiskTool meets the needs of pupils and teachers, and what adjustments will be necessary to optimise its applicability in mathematics teaching. The teacher needs assessment may further provide valuable information regarding the requirements for integrating microlearning modules on health topics as application examples in mathematics lessons. Teachers may express preferences regarding time requirements, curricular integration, and didactic approaches, as well as potential barriers to implementation.

References

1. Park E, Kwon M. Health-Related Internet Use by Children and Adolescents: Systematic Review. *J Med Internet Res*. 2018; 20:e120. doi:10.2196/jmir.7731.
2. Freeman JL, Caldwell PHY, Bennett PA, Scott KM. How Adolescents Search for and Appraise Online Health Information: A Systematic Review. *J Pediatr*. 2018; 195:244-255.e1. doi:10.1016/j.jpeds.2017.11.031.
3. World Health Organization (WHO). Munich Security Conference. 2020. <https://www.who.int/director-general/speeches/detail/munich-security-conference>. Accessed 12 Mar 2025.
4. Oxman AD, Chalmers I, Dahlgren A. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices (Version 2022): Zenodo; 2022.
5. Nutbeam D. Health literacy as a public health goal: a challenge for contemporary health education and communication strategies into the 21st century. *Health Promotion International*. 2000; 15:259–67. doi:10.1093/heapro/15.3.259.
6. Hinneburg J, Steckelber A. Kritische Gesundheitskompetenz. *Ausweg aus der fremdverschuldeten Unmündigkeit*; 2018.
7. Schaeffer, D., Hurrelmann, K., Bauer, U. und. Nationaler Aktionsplan Gesundheitskompetenz: Die Gesundheitskompetenz in Deutschland stärken. Berlin: KomPart; 2018.
8. World Health Organization (WHO) Regional Office for Europe. Health literacy in the context of health, wellbeing and learning outcomes – the case of children and adolescents in schools: a concept paper; 2021.
9. Ringle VAM, Dahlgren A, Rosenbaum S, Jensen-Doss A. Critical thinking about health and treatments in the United States: a cross-sectional assessment of parents and undergraduate college students. *BMC Public Health*. 2025; 25:336. doi: 10.1186/s12889-025-21291-9.
10. Moxey A, O'Connell D, McGettigan P, Henry D. Describing treatment effects to patients. *J Gen Intern Med*. 2003; 18:948–59. doi:10.1046/j.1525-1497.2003.20928.x.
11. Edwards A, Elwyn G, Covey J, Matthews E, Pill R. Presenting risk information--a review of the effects of "framing" and other manipulations on patient outcomes. *J Health Commun*. 2001; 6:61–82. doi: 10.1080/10810730150501413.
12. Dahlgren A, Furuseth-Olsen K, Rose CJ, Oxman AD. The Norwegian public's ability to assess treatment claims: results of a cross-sectional study of critical health literacy. *F1000Res*. 2020; 9:179. doi:10.12688/f1000research.21902.2.
13. Akl EA, Oxman AD, Herrin J, Vist GE, Terrenato I, Sperati F, et al. Using alternative statistical formats for presenting risks and risk reductions. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2011; 2011:CD006776. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD006776.pub2.
14. Chesire F, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, Rose CJ, Nsangi A, Kaseje M, et al. Effects of the Informed Health Choices secondary school intervention: A prospective meta-analysis. *J Evid Based Med*. 2023; 16:321–31. doi:10.1111/jebm.12552.

15. Rosenbaum S, Moberg J, Chesire F, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, Ochieng MA, et al. Teaching critical thinking about health information and choices in secondary schools: human-centred design of digital resources. *F1000Res*. 2023; 12:481. doi:10.12688/f1000research.132580.3.
16. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Rosenbaum SE, Oxman AD, Oxman M, Morelli A, et al. Development of the informed health choices resources in four countries to teach primary school children to assess claims about treatment effects: a qualitative study employing a user-centred approach. *Pilot Feasibility Stud*. 2020; 6:18. doi:10.1186/s40814-020-00565-6.
17. Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Oxman M, Rosenbaum S, et al. Effects of the Informed Health Choices primary school intervention on the ability of children in Uganda to assess the reliability of claims about treatment effects: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2017; 390:374–88. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(17)31226-6.
18. Taylor A-d, Hung W. The Effects of Microlearning: A Scoping Review. *Education Tech Research Dev*. 2022; 70:363–95. doi: 10.1007/s11423-022-10084-1.
19. Zacher S, Berger-Höger B, Lühnen J, Steckelberg A. Development and Piloting of a Web-Based Tool to Teach Relative and Absolute Risk Reductions. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2022. doi:10.3390/ijerph192316086.
20. Ministerium für Bildung des Landes Sachsen-Anhalt. Fachlehrplan Sekundarschule: Mathematik. 2019. https://lisa.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/MK/LISA/Unterricht/Lehrplaene/Sek/Anpassung/lp_sks_mathe_01_08_2019.pdf. Accessed 6 Mar 2025.
21. Informed Health Choices. Key Concepts for assessing claims about treatment effects and making well-informed treatment choices: 2.3b Be cautious of relative effects of treatments alone. 2022. <https://www.informedhealthchoices.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/2.3b-Be-cautious-of-relative-effects-of-treatments-alone.pdf>. Accessed 6 Mar 2025.
22. Vargas C, Whelan J, Brimblecombe J, Allender S. Co-creation, co-design, co-production for public health - a perspective on definition and distinctions. *Public Health Res Pract* 2022. doi: 10.17061/phrp3222211.
23. Skivington K, Matthews L, Simpson SA, Craig P, Baird J, Blazeby JM, et al. A new framework for developing and evaluating complex interventions: update of Medical Research Council guidance. *BMJ*. 2021; 374:n2061. doi:10.1136/bmj.n2061.
24. Sandro Zacher & RiskTool-Team. RiskTool - Vermittlung relative und absolute Risikoreduktion. 2025. <https://www.leitlinie-gesundheitsinformation.de/Schulungsmaterial/risktool/#Start>. Accessed 3 Mar 2025.
25. Knowles M. *The adult learners: A neglected species*. Houston: Gulf Publishing Co. 1990.
26. Branch RM, Varank İ. *Instructional design: The ADDIE approach*: Springer; 2009.
27. Keller JM. *Motivational design for learning and performance: The ARCS model approach*: Springer Science & Business Media; 2009.
28. Mayer RE. Using multimedia for e-learning. *Journal of computer assisted learning*. 2017; 33:403–23.
29. Bowen DJ, Kreuter M, Spring B, Cofta-Woerpel L, Linnan L, Weiner D, et al. How we design feasibility studies. *Am J Prev Med*. 2009; 36:452–7. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2009.02.002.

30. Zacher, S., Berger-Höger, B., Kasper, J., Lühnen, J. & Steckelberg, A. The competence to critically appraise risk reductions - a validation study (#145825). 2023. <https://aspredicted.org/uv67i.pdf>. Accessed 6 Mar 2025.
31. Mayring P. Grundlagen und Techniken. Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. 2015; 12.
32. Rasch G. Probabilistic models for some intelligence and achievement tests. Copenhagen: Danish Institute for Educational Research; 1960.